

Floral diversity of Deomali hills, Koraput, Odisha, India

Sanjeet Kumar

Biodiversity and Conservation Lab., Ambika Prasad Research Foundation, Odisha, India

E-mail: sanjeetaprf@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9538-397X>

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Deomali hill, situated in Koraput district of Odisha state, India which rises to 1,672 metres above sea level, making it the highest peak in the state. Forming part of the Eastern Ghats, it is characterised by a unique high-elevation tableland with gently undulating, grass-clad plateaus, rocky exposures, sharp escarpments and sweeping views of surrounding valleys (Figure 1). The hill's cool weather, windy conditions and diverse mix of grasslands, montane forests and seasonal watercourses sustain a rich and varied floral diversity including several threatened species. Deomali hills areas also holds strong cultural and spiritual importance for indigenous communities, whose traditions, beliefs and folklore are deeply connected to this landscape (Kumar et al., 2025). Author has visited Deomali areas in the year 2025 and enumerated available plant species.

Figure 1: Panoramic view of Deomali hills, Koraput, Odisha, India

The hill areas support a total of about 339 plant species from 90 families, with the tableland itself harbouring about 104 species including about 25 invasive plant species and about 19 major weeds

along with 21 priority species requiring urgent conservation attention like *Drosera peltata*, *Hypericum gaitii*, *Osyris lanceolata* and *Gnetum edule*. Despite its ecological value, Deomali hill areas faces mounting human-induced pressures such as plastic waste from unmanaged tourism, habitat disturbance from road widening, frequent forest fires, the spread of invasive weeds and illegal harvesting of plant resources, all of which threaten its fragile ecosystems. Most common plant species of hill areas are *Abelmoschus angulosus*, *Acrocarpus fraxinifolius*, *Acronychia pedunculata*, *Adenostemma lavenia*, *Ageratina adenophora*, *Alstonia venenata*, *Apluda mutica*, *Boehmeria macrophylla*, *Carex baccans*, *Colebrookea oppositifolia*, *Cymbopogon citratus*, *Corymbia citriodora*, *Dalbergia latifolia*, *Debregeasia longifolia*, *Drosera peltata*, *Eucalyptus globulus*, *Ficus auriculata*, *Ficus palmata*, *Gnetum edule*, *Gymnosphaera gigantea*, *Gymnosporia rothiana*, *Hemionitis arifolia*, *Homalium napaulense*, *Hypericum gaitii*, *Macaranga peltata*, *Mappia nimmoniana*, *Nervilia plicata*, *Oreocnide integrifolia*, *Osyris lanceolata*, *Phoenix acaulis*, *Pogostemon quadrifolius*, *Rubus ellipticus*, *Rubus treutleri*, *Salvia misella*, *Santalum album*, *Smitinandia micrantha*, *Terminalia bellirica*, *Thalictrum foliolosum*, *Themeda quadrivalvis*, *Thysanolaena latifolia*, *Zanthoxylum armatum*, etc. (Saxena and Brahmam, 1994-1996). Some tree species are documented in Plate 1. Protecting the Deomali tableland and adjoining areas calls for the restoration of native vegetation, effective management of invasive species and strict regulation of ecotourism.

Plate 1: Some common tree species of Deomali hill areas, Koraput, Odisha; a) *Acronychia pedunculata*, b) *Debregeasia longifolia*, c) *Ficus auriculata*, d) *Ficus palmata*, e) *Gymnosporia rothiana*, f) *Mappia nimmoniana*, g) *Oreocnide integrifolia*, h) *Osyris lanceolata* and i) *Santalum album*

Emphasis should be placed on planting robust, climate-tolerant species like *Apluda mutica*, *Themeda triandra*, *Calotropis gigantea*, *Cassia fistula* and *Dalbergia sissoo* to reduce soil erosion, enhance biodiversity and improve roadside stability. These ecological actions need to be supported by proper waste disposal systems, provision of dustbins and drinking water, a total prohibition on polythene use and routine weed clearance. Conserving rare and vulnerable plants like *Hypericum gaitii*, carnivorous species and parasitic herbs will require strong enforcement of conservation laws, protection of habitats and responsible eco-tourism with active community participation. Involving local youth as nature guides, strengthening environmental education, encouraging sustainable traditional resource use and hosting community-driven events can help build long-term management and secure a sustainable future for Deomali hill areas of Koraput, Odisha, India.

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